

Indian Healing Tradition- Past, Present And It's Relevance: An Exposition

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The knowledge of medical value of plants and other substances dates back to the time of great antiquity. The vast knowledge of medical science that has come down to the span of modern era is the result of a long evolution through different stages. Indian traditional healing systems have a very rich history of their fruitfulness and are progressively becoming admired across the world. The hymns of the Vedic Samhitas are the earliest literary sources of knowledge regarding the healing practices in Ancient India. Insights into different ailments widespread at that time and their apparent causes are seen to be well provided in the Vedic hymns. The Atharvaveda Samhita, the last of the four Vedas can be termed to be the first available text where a huge number of preventive and curative practices are found to be quoted with elaborate descriptions. Whereas the applause of the sprouting seeds of medical tradition goes unanimously to the pages of the Rgveda Samhita which is credited and well proved to be the composition of not later than 7000 B.C.

Through this paper a modest effort is intended to be done with a view to present a discussion on healing tradition prevalent in Ancient India and its progress in various regions of this subcontinent in later times.

Key words: traditional medicine, Vedic Samhita, Ayurveda, India, Medicinal Plants.